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The benefits of inclusive education: a systematic review of student achievement in secondary schools

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ABSTRACT

Despite efforts to increase inclusion in education, little research exists on its impact at the lower secondary level (ages 11–17). This paper presents a systematic review of the literature on the academic achievement of secondary school students with special educational needs (SEN) and their peers in inclusive education. A search of publications in English, French, and German on seven databases (ERIC, PsychInfo, PsychArticles, SCOPUS, Web of Science, CAIRN, FIS) identified 21 eligible studies. The results reveal that students with SEN have higher achievement and make more academic progress in inclusive settings. Most studies found that students without SEN are not disadvantaged by inclusive settings, although the proportion of students with SEN in a class seems to be important. It is possible that the results reflect a placement effect, where students with less severe special educational needs are more likely to be placed in inclusive settings. More research is needed to increase knowledge of the effects of inclusive education on secondary students with and without SEN.

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Inclusive education; special educational needs (SEN); secondary school; academic achievement; systematic review

Introduction

In recent years, the proportion of students with special educational needs (SEN) educated in inclusive secondary school classes has increased (Williamson et al. 2020). However, students with SEN are still more likely to be placed in special classes or schools in secondary school than in primary (Williamson et al. 2020). Despite the increase at the secondary level, there has been relatively little research into the impact of the inclusive education of students with SEN on secondary student achievement. Existing meta-analyses and reviews often include research on both primary and secondary education (Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015; Dalgaard et al. 2022; Kalambouka et al. 2007; Kart and Kart 2021; Oh-Young and Filler 2015; Ruijs and Peetsma 2009), making it difficult to draw specific conclusions about secondary school students. Many studies of secondary school students also place a greater emphasis on the effect of inclusion on social participation than academic success (Van Mieghem et al. 2018).

Most research on inclusive education takes one of two approaches. It either focuses exclusively on students with SEN and examines differences in achievement between

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students in different settings (e.g. special schools vs. general education) or it compares the impact of inclusion on students with SEN with the impact on their peers without SEN (Ge and Zhang 2019). None of the existing analyses have considered both the potential impact of different educational settings and compared students with and without SEN. This systematic review aims to fill a gap in the current body of research by examining the literature on the achievement of secondary students (ages 11 – 17) in inclusive education. The review includes studies that compare students with and without SEN in inclusive settings with those in non-inclusive settings and studies examining the effects of inclusive settings on students with and without SEN.¹

Conceptual clarification

The terminology for students with SEN varies across countries and fields (Lindsay 2007). In this review, SEN refers to students identified as having special needs if no specification is mentioned. Specific types follow the German classification: learning difficulties (LD), emotional and social difficulties (ESD), language impairment (LI), intellectual disabilities (ID), hearing impairment (HI), visual impairment (VI), and physical and motor impairment (PI) (Kultusministerkonferenz 2021). Students without identification are referred to as students without SEN.

Inclusive education broadly describes the teaching of students with SEN in mainstream classes (Göransson and Nilholm 2014). This can be full inclusion (all students taught together) or partial inclusion (some separate instruction) (Ruijs and Peetsma 2009). Since many studies do not specify the exact setting, we use inclusive education to mean that students with and without SEN are taught together. Non-inclusive refers to settings where students with SEN are taught exclusively in separate classes or schools.

Challenges of inclusive education in secondary schools

Implementing inclusive education in secondary schools seems to be more challenging than implementing it in primary schools (Pearce and Forlin 2005). According to Woodcock and Jones the opportunities for flexibility, adaptivity, or differentiation required by inclusive practice may be limited by ‘a regime ruled by timetables and teacher time’ (Woodcock and Jones 2020, 588). Some secondary teachers only see their students for a short time each week, making it more difficult for them to recognise and respond to student needs (De Vroey, Struyf, and Petry 2016; Pearce and Forlin 2005; Szumski, Smogorzewska, and Karwowski 2017). The separation of students into vocational and academic streams and ability tracking based on achievement in many secondary school systems also conflicts with inclusive values (De Vroey, Struyf, and Petry 2016).

There are features of secondary schooling that make learning more difficult for students with SEN. Whole-class teaching is valued, with students expected to independently manage their learning, organise their belongings, and complete homework – tasks that are particularly challenging for students with SEN (Pearce and Forlin 2005). There is also a greater focus on content knowledge. This is partly a result of how secondary teachers are trained and partly a response to the demanding secondary curriculum (Pearce and Forlin 2005). Because secondary schools prepare students for higher education or the labour market they often

face public and political scrutiny (De Vroey, Struyf, and Petry 2016). This can result in priorities that conflict with special support for students with SEN (Bulgren et al. 2006). There is also some concern that students with and without SEN may learn less in inclusive settings because the increased heterogeneity of the classroom makes it difficult to meet their learning needs (Round, Subban, and Sharma 2015).

Results of previous reviews

Meta-analyses and reviews have investigated the effect of the inclusive education of students with SEN on the academic achievement of students with SEN, students without SEN, or both. Oh-Young and Filler's (2015) meta-analysis of primary and secondary school students found that students with SEN in inclusive settings who spent one period per day in a resource room performed significantly better in academic achievement than those who were taught for more than one period per day in self-contained classrooms, schools, or resource rooms. Szumski, Smogorzewska, and Karwowski (2017) conducted a meta-analysis of the effect of the presence of students with SEN on the academic achievement of students without SEN in secondary schools. All effects were either neutral or positive.

Three reviews looked at the effects of inclusive education on the achievement of students with SEN in primary and secondary school (Dalgaard et al. 2022; Gebhardt 2015; Ruijs and Peetsma 2009). Gebhardt (2015) reported that teaching students with SEN in inclusive classrooms had a positive effect on achievement and achievement gains compared to teaching them in special classes. Ruijs and Peetsma (2009) showed that most studies found positive or neutral effects for students with SEN. Dalgaard et al. (2022) found no sizeable positive or negative effects of inclusive education on the academic achievement of students with SEN.

De Vroey, Struyf, and Petry (2016) reviewed studies on students with SEN in secondary schools. They found that students with SEN taught in mainstream classes had higher achievement than those taught in special classes. However, the results were less consistent for students with emotional and social difficulties.

Reviews have also examined the impact of inclusive education on the academic achievement of students without SEN in primary and secondary schools (Gebhardt 2015; Kalambouka et al. 2007; Kart and Kart 2021; Ruijs and Peetsma 2009). Gebhardt's (2015) review did not find any significant difference in the academic achievement of students without SEN taught in inclusive settings and those taught in non-inclusive ones. Kalambouka et al. (2007) and Ruijs and Peetsma (2009) found that most studies reported positive or neutral effects for the academic achievement of students without SEN being taught with students with SEN. A literature review by Kart and Kart (2021) revealed that inclusive education had mostly positive or neutral effects on students without SEN in preschool and primary school but neutral or negative effects in secondary school.

There is an interesting difference between the results of studies on the education outcomes of inclusion conducted in the USA and those conducted in Europe. US studies, often based on large-scale national testing, report mostly positive effects, while European studies with smaller samples tend to report more neutral effects (Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015; Szumski, Smogorzewska, and Grygiel 2022).

Study aims

Our literature review shows that meta-analyses and reviews of the inclusive education of students with SEN in secondary school have investigated different, often mixed, groups (primary and secondary school students, students with and without SEN) in a variety of settings (comparison of inclusive and non-inclusive settings; inclusive settings only), making it difficult to draw conclusions about the actual impact of inclusion on secondary student's achievement. The reviews and meta-analyses have also focused on studies written in English.

This study aims to address this research gap by conducting a systematic review of student academic achievement in the context of inclusive education. It seeks to answer the following question:

What are the effects of inclusive education of students with SEN on the academic achievement of both students with and without SEN in secondary school?

The following features characterise this review. First, it focuses exclusively on secondary school. Second, to counteract some of the language bias (Brunton et al. 2017), studies published in English, French, and German are reviewed. Third, it includes studies comparing the achievement of students with and without SEN in inclusive and non-inclusive settings and studies examining the achievement of students with and without SEN in inclusive settings.

Methods

The study follows the updated PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis) guidelines (Page et al. 2021). The research question was the starting point for the literature search.

Literature search

As a first step, a search using relevant terms was conducted in the ERIC, PsychInfo, PsychArticles, SCOPUS, Web of Science, CAIRN and FIS databases. Then, references found in previous reviews and those known to the authors were added manually.

The search terms were derived from the keywords inclusive education, special educational needs, secondary school, and academic achievement (see Table 1 for a full list of search terms and syntax). They were also translated into French and German. The search

Table 1. Search strategy.^a

Search term combination and syntax
'inclus*' OR 'integrat*' OR 'mainstream*' OR 'general*' OR 'regular*'
AND 'special* need*' OR 'disabilit*' OR 'difficult*'
AND 'middle school' OR 'secondary*' OR 'lower high school'
AND 'student outcome*' OR 'academic achievement*' OR 'academic performance*' OR «academic progress*» OR «attainment» OR «academic competence*» OR 'ability' OR 'effects' OR 'impact' OR 'outcome'

^aThe strategy was adapted for searches in the different databases.

was limited to peer-reviewed academic journals written in English, French, and German. Only studies from 2006 to 2025, post-UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations 2006), were included. The search was conducted in March 2025.

Inclusion-exclusion criteria

To be included, a study had to fulfil the following criteria:

- (1) It had to only include secondary school students (ages 11 – 17);
- (2) It had to report student achievement;
- (3) It had to be conducted in the context of inclusive education.

Because these content-specific criteria would limit the selection, no methodological criteria were defined.

A study was excluded if:

- (1) It was not written in English, French, or German;
- (2) It was a review or meta-analysis;
- (3) It was not empirical;
- (4) The results focused on students who were not in secondary school;
- (5) If only post-secondary outcomes (e.g. post-school participation) or outcomes concerning the perceptions or attitudes of teachers or students were reported.

Intervention studies that investigated, for example, the influence of co-teaching or peer learning on student achievement in inclusive classes were also excluded.

Selection process

Figure 1 shows a PRISMA flowchart of the selection process. A total of 3,691 studies were identified. Duplicates were manually removed. The titles and abstracts of the 1,504 remaining articles were screened to ensure they satisfied the selection criteria (Brunton et al. 2017), resulting in a shortlist of 37 articles for further screening.

To ensure reliability, a second rater was trained to apply the inclusion-exclusion criteria and the screening procedure (Gough, Oliver, and Thomas 2017). The first author and the rater independently assessed 25% of the studies ($n = 338$), achieving substantial interrater reliability ($\kappa = 0.730$; Landis and Koch 1977). Discrepancies were discussed, and criteria were refined until full agreement was reached. The first author then screened the remaining titles and abstracts alone.

For the full-text screening of 37 articles, both raters jointly coded one study, then independently assessed 25% ($n = 10$), achieving 90% agreement. The first author screened the remaining texts alone.

Of the 37 articles selected for full-text screening, 17 were excluded based on the inclusion-exclusion criteria. A review of the reference lists of the 20 remaining studies (Brunton et al. 2017) yielded four additional articles which were reviewed and found to be

Figure 1. PRISMA flow chart.

suitable for further analysis. Full-text screening of eligible articles resulted in 24 articles to be assessed for quality.

Quality assessment

We used the Methodological Quality Questionnaire to assess the studies and train the second rater (Acosta et al. 2020). Both raters jointly assessed one study, then independently rated another. The agreement between the two was 83.3%. The second rater evaluated a random subsample (7 of 24 studies), while the first author assessed the remaining articles.

Afterwards, both raters decided which studies met the criteria. Three studies were excluded: one for a low-quality research design (e.g. inconsistent data sources) and two for lacking relevance to inclusive education. Any remaining issues were discussed. At the end of the process, we were left with 21 studies.

Data extraction

The following information was recorded for each of the 21 studies: first author, publication year and country, sample characteristics (group of students, type of SEN, number of participants), study design (cross-sectional vs. longitudinal), type of achievement (e.g. maths), how achievement was assessed (scores, grades), and key findings.

Procedure for coding the results

The key achievement outcome reported by each study was coded as a positive (+incl), negative (–incl), mixed (\pm incl), or neutral effect of inclusive education (= incl) in line with Lindsay (2007) and Begeny and Martens (2007). Outcomes were coded as positive if results indicated that the achievement of the group of interest (students with SEN or students without SEN) was higher in an inclusive setting than in a non-inclusive setting or if the achievement or the achievement gain of the group of interest was positive in an inclusive setting. The outcome was assessed as negative if the achievement of the group of interest was lower in an inclusive than in a non-inclusive setting or if those students' achievement or achievement gains were lower. Where positive and negative effects (e.g. for different subjects) were reported, it was coded as a mixed inclusion effect. Outcomes were coded as neutral if no differences were found.

Results

Descriptive characteristics of the selected studies

The review included studies from the following countries: USA ($n = 7$), Germany ($n = 3$), United Kingdom ($n = 3$), Australia, Austria, China, Finland, the Netherlands, Poland, Singapore and Switzerland ($n = 1$ study in each country). Eleven studies had been conducted in English-speaking countries (Australia, UK, USA), eight in non-English speaking European countries, and two in Asia (China, Singapore). All but one study had been published in English.

Study participants were secondary school students (ages 11 – 17) with a range of SEN: learning difficulties (LD; $n = 4$), hearing impairment (HI, $n = 3$), physical impairment (PI, $n = 1$), language impairment (LI, $n = 2$), emotional and social difficulties (ESD, $n = 2$), and intellectual disabilities (ID, $n = 2$). In one study, students with HI, SLI and PI were referred to as having functional disabilities (FD, $n = 1$). In seven studies, the group of students with SEN was not further defined or students with different types of SEN were considered together. Seven studies focused on students without SEN.

All included studies had a quantitative research design ($n = 21$). Eleven were cross-sectional, and 10 were longitudinal.

Fourteen studies compared achievement in inclusive and non-inclusive settings. The other seven examined the effects of inclusive settings on the achievement of students with and without SEN.

Achievement of students in inclusive education

Because the studies vary in design, outcome measures, and statistical reporting, we are presenting the results as a narrative systematic review. Studies included in the review are listed in [Tables 2 and 3](#). [Table 2](#) lists studies comparing the academic achievement of students with and without SEN in inclusive and non-inclusive settings. [Table 3](#) lists studies examining the effects of inclusive settings on the achievement of students with and without SEN.

Students with SEN benefit from inclusive education

The majority of the studies reported that students with SEN in inclusive settings demonstrated higher academic achievement than those in non-inclusive settings (Barrett, Stevenson, and Burns 2020; Buckley et al. 2006; Cole et al. 2023; Durkin et al. 2009; Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015; Marschark et al. 2015; Turner, Alborz, and Gayle 2008; Vosganoff, Paatsch, and Toe 2011). Some observed no significant difference in achievement between inclusive and non-inclusive settings (Barrocas and Cramer 2014; Hienonen, Hotulainen, and Jahnukainen 2020; Jungjohann, Schurig, and Gebhardt 2023; Malhotra 2024). None of the studies reported a negative effect of inclusion for students with SEN.

Research on academic progress also suggests that inclusive settings are beneficial. Three studies found greater achievement gains for students with SEN in inclusive settings compared to those studying in non-inclusive settings (Buckley et al. 2006; Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015; Turner, Alborz, and Gayle 2008), whereas one study (Barrocas and Cramer 2014) reported no significant differences in achievement gains between the two settings.

Longitudinal studies conducted in inclusive settings reported consistent or improved achievement in students with SEN in inclusive settings (Antia et al. 2009; Ge and Zhang 2019; Schwab et al. 2015; Stiefel et al. 2021).

Inclusive education benefits students with different types of SEN

Although the type of SEN is an important factor when studying the effects of inclusive education, only a few of the studies considered it. Most studies either investigated heterogeneous groups of *students with SEN* or did not provide information about the type of SEN. Studies that investigated effects on students with unspecified or a range of

Table 2. Effect on achievement: inclusive vs. non-inclusive settings ($n = 14$).

Study	Sample ^a with SEN ^b secondary school	Study Design	Students	Student outcomes	Comparison	Inclusion Effect
Students with SEN Barrett, Stephenson, and Burns (2020), USA	^a 3,796	cross-sectional	SEN	Maths, ELA	More time spent in general education setting vs. less time spent in general education setting	+ incl
Buckley et al. (2006), UK	^a 136	longitudinal	ID	Communication skills (including reading and writing)	Mainstream classrooms vs. special education classrooms	+ incl
Cole et al. (2023), USA	^a 23,796 (ELA), ^a 23,940 (maths)	cross-sectional	SEN	Maths, ELA	High inclusion settings (>80% of the time) vs. low inclusion settings (<80% of the time)	+ incl
Durkin et al. (2009), UK	241 ^a 120	cross-sectional	LI	Maths, English, science	Mainstream classes vs. special setting/special school	+ incl
Gebhardt et al. (2015), GER	^a 902	longitudinal	LD ESD FD	Maths, reading, science	Inclusive setting vs. special school	+ incl + incl + incl
Hienonen, Hotulainen, and Jahnukainen (2020), FIN	^a 268	cross-sectional	SEN	Maths, Finnish	Regular vs. special classes	= incl
Jungjohann, Schurig, and Gebhardt (2023), GER	1,066 ^a 392	cross-sectional	LD, LI	Reading	Inclusive schools vs. special schools	= incl
Marschark et al. (2015), USA	^a 500	cross-sectional	HI	Comprehension, maths calculations, science & social science	Regular schools (including self-contained classrooms) vs. special schools	+ incl + incl
Turner, Alborz, and Gayle (2008), UK	^a 71	longitudinal	ID	Numeracy, reading, writing	Regular schools (including self-contained classrooms) vs. mix of regular and special schools	+ incl
Vosganoff, Paatsch, and Toe (2011), AUS	^a 16	cross-sectional	HI	Maths, science	Mainstream schools vs. special schools	+ incl
Students without SEN					Full mainstream classes vs. partial mainstreamed classes	+ incl
Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer (2015), GER	9,923 ^a 244	cross-sectional	w/o SEN	Maths, reading, science	Inclusive vs. regular classes	= incl
Szumski, Smogorzewska, and Grygiel (2022), POL	1171 ^a 174	longitudinal	w/o SEN	Maths, Polish language	Inclusive vs. non-inclusive classrooms	= incl
Students with and without SEN						

(Continued)

Table 2. (Continued).

Study	Sample ^a with SEN ^b secondary school	Study Design	Students	Student outcomes	Comparison	Inclusion Effect
Barrocas & Cramer (2014), USA	160 ^a 80	longitudinal	LD w/o SEN	Maths, reading	Inclusive vs. segregated settings	= incl = incl
Malhotra (2024), USA	NR	cross-sectional	SEN w/o SEN	Maths, ELA	Inclusive vs. non-inclusive education	= incl = incl = incl

LD = learning difficulties; ESD = emotional and social difficulties; LI = language impairment; ID = intellectual disabilities; HI = hearing impairment; PI = physical impairment; FD = functional disability (includes students with HI, LI and PI); ELA = English language arts.
SEN = special educational needs; w/o SEN = students without SEN; NR = not reported.

Table 3. Effect on achievement: inclusive settings ($n = 7$).

Study	Sample a with SEN b secondary school	Study Design	Students	Student outcomes	Comparison	Inclusion Effect
Students with SEN Antia et al. (2009), USA	^a 197	longitudinal	HI	Maths, reading, language/ writing	t1 vs. t2	+ incl
Schwab et al. (2015), GER	54 ^a 18	longitudinal	SEN	Reading ability	t1 vs. t2 SEN (t1-t2) vs. low IQ (t1-t2) Progress students with SEN vs. progress students w/o SEN	+ incl - incl - incl
Stiefel et al. (2021), USA	2.8 Mil. ^a 0.5 Mio.	longitudinal	SEN	Maths, ELA	t1 vs. t2 Progress students with SEN vs. progress students w/o SEN	+ incl - incl - incl
Yeo & Tan (2018), SGP	60 ^a ^b 12	cross-sectional	PI	Maths, English	SEN vs. w/o SEN PD vs. w/o SEN	± incl
Students without SEN Ruijs (2017), NED	518,985 ^a 5,472	cross-sectional	w/o SEN	Multiple subjects	Presence SEN Presence VI/Hi/PD/ID/EBS High vs. low proportion of SEN students in class	= incl = incl = incl
Students with and without SEN Balestra, Eugster, and Liebert (2022), SUI	49,961 ^a 8,293 (LD); 2,997 (SEBD)	cross-sectional	LD, ESD w/o SEN	Maths, German Maths, German	LD vs. EBD SEN present (< 15–20%) High proportion (> 15–20%) SEN students in class vs. low	- incl = incl - incl = incl
Ge & Zhang (2019), CHN	8,252 ^a 635	longitudinal	SEN w/o SEN	Cognitive abilities	SEN present (< 15–20%) High proportion (> 15–20%) SEN students in class t1 vs. t2 t1 vs. t2 progress students with SEN vs. Progress students w/ o SEN	+ incl + incl = incl

LD = learning difficulties; ESD = emotional and social difficulties; HI = hearing impairment; PI = physical impairment; ELA = English language arts. SEN = special educational needs; w/o SEN = students without SEN. t1 = first measurement time; t2 = second measurement time.

SEN reported neutral effects (Hienonen, Hotulainen, and Jahnukainen 2020; Malhotra 2024) or indicated that the students benefitted from inclusive settings by showing higher academic achievement than in special education settings (Barrett, Stevenson, and Burns 2020; Cole et al. 2023).

The gains in achievement of students with LD, ESD, and ID in inclusive settings were found to be greater than (Buckley et al. 2006; Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015; Turner, Alborz, and Gayle 2008) or equal to (Barrocas and Cramer 2014; Jungjohann, Schurig, and Gebhardt 2023) that of similar students in special education settings. Studies also reported that students with SLI and with HI in inclusive settings outperformed (Durkin et al. 2009; Marschark et al. 2015; Vosganoff, Paatsch, and Toe 2011) or equalled (Jungjohann, Schurig, and Gebhardt 2023) the performance of those in special education settings. These students also progressed more in inclusive than in special education settings (Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015).

Finally, studies comparing students with SEN in inclusive settings to those without SEN confirmed that students with SEN (Stiefel et al. 2021) had lower achievement. Students with SEN either progressed less than those without (Schwab et al. 2015; Stiefel et al. 2021) or there was no difference in progress rates (Ge and Zhang 2019). But the type of SEN and the subject are important. Students with PI had significantly lower scores in maths than their peers but not in English (Yeo and Tan 2018).

Partial versus full inclusion, does it make a difference?

Four studies comparing the academic achievement of students with SEN in full inclusion versus partial inclusion settings found that full inclusion led to better results. Students with SEN – in two studies, students with HI – achieved higher academic levels in full inclusion settings than in partial settings (Barrett, Stevenson, and Burns 2020; Cole et al. 2023; Marschark et al. 2015; Vosganoff, Paatsch, and Toe 2011). However, only two of the studies defined full inclusion. In Barrett, Stevenson, and Burns (2020) full inclusion meant students with SEN were in the same classroom as their peers without SEN during the whole school day. In Cole et al. (2023) they were together at least 80% of the teaching day.

Neutral effects of inclusive education on students without SEN

Cross-sectional analyses and longitudinal studies consistently demonstrated that students without SEN are not academically disadvantaged when taught with peers with SEN in inclusive settings (Barrocas and Cramer 2014; Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015; Malhotra 2024; Szumski, Smogorzewska, and Grygiel 2022).

Two studies investigated whether the proportion of students with SEN per class affects the academic achievement of those without (Balestra, Eugster, and Liebert 2022; Ruijs 2017). Balestra, Eugster, and Liebert (2022) reported a threshold effect. When more than 15–20% of students in the class had SEN, a negative effect on the academic achievement of peers was observed, except for those in the top quartile. This effect was moderate and not present in all classes. Ruijs (2017) found no evidence that a higher proportion of students with SEN in inclusive classrooms affected the academic achievement of those without.

Discussion

Our systematic review of the literature investigating the effects of inclusive education on the academic achievement of students with and without SEN in secondary school was based on 21 studies that fulfilled our inclusion criteria. It revealed that the academic achievement of students with SEN in inclusive settings is either at the same level or higher than in non-inclusive settings. These results are in line with Gebhardt (2015), who also reported generally positive effects for the achievement of students with SEN in inclusive secondary classrooms.

Several factors may explain these results. Mainstream classes often have a higher pace of learning and more ambitious curricula than special classes (Buckley et al. 2006). Teachers in mainstream settings also tend to have greater expectations of their students with SEN, which can boost achievement, particularly in secondary schools where teachers have subject specialisms (Pearce and Forlin 2005). The presence of SEN students in mainstream classes fosters teacher adaptivity, which benefits all students (Farrell et al. 2007). However, some of the higher achievement noted in inclusive settings may be due to a *placement effect*, an effect arising from the tendency to place students with milder cognitive impairment (e.g. mild or moderate learning difficulties) in mainstream classes and those with more severe disabilities (e.g. intellectual disabilities or autism spectrum disorder) in special education settings (Hienonen, Hotulainen, and Jahnukainen 2020; Marschark et al. 2015). It can mean that the apparent advantage for students with SEN reflects differences in cognitive abilities rather than setting. However, this factor is rarely considered in studies on the effects of inclusive education in secondary schools. More longitudinal data is needed to answer this question.

As expected, the academic achievement level of students with SEN in inclusive settings was lower than that of students without (Schwab et al. 2015; Stiefel et al. 2021). However, this was not true for students with PI (Yeo and Tan 2018). Academic achievement depends on the cognitive potential of the student, which may or may not be a factor for students with PI.

In the studies reviewed, students with HI and ID achieved better outcomes in inclusive settings than in special education settings. However, there is evidence that some students with HI and ID prefer being taught in special settings (Byrnes 2011). This means that factors other than achievement must be considered when discussing inclusive education. While no negative effects were observed for students with ESD, our findings differ from those of De Vroey, Struyf, and Petry (2016), who reported inconsistent outcomes for students with ESD.

Studies found that the achievement of students with LD, SLI, and PI in inclusive settings was equal to or greater than similar students in special education settings (Barrocas and Cramer 2014; Durkin et al. 2009; Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015; Jungjohann, Schurig, and Gebhardt 2023). This finding aligns with the results of the literature review by De Vroey, Struyf, and Petry (2016). But we cannot make further generalisations because few of the studies focused on a specific type of SEN. Given that the type and severity of SEN can affect academic achievement, researchers should be encouraged to give precise descriptions of the students they are studying.

Students taught in full inclusion demonstrated higher academic achievement than those taught in partial inclusion settings (Barrett, Stevenson, and Burns 2020; Cole et al.

2023; Marschark et al. 2015; Vosganoff, Paatsch, and Toe 2011). These results are in line with the meta-analysis by Oh-Young and Filler (2015) which revealed that students taught in mainstream settings outperformed those taught in self-contained classrooms. One possible explanation for this is that the positive aspects of inclusive settings, such as higher expectations from teachers and student aspiration, have more influence when students are in the mainstream classroom for longer periods. Unfortunately, most studies did not report how much time students with SEN spent in the inclusive classroom.

Several studies found that students without SEN in inclusive secondary schools did not have lower academic achievement or progress than students taught in non-inclusive classrooms. These findings are in line with those of other reviews and meta-analyses (Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015; Kalambouka et al. 2007; Kart and Kart 2021; Szumski, Smogorzewska, and Karwowski 2017). It can be assumed that teachers who adapt lessons to the individual needs of students with SEN are able to also tailor their teaching for all students (Farrell et al. 2007).

Finally, the review revealed some contradictory findings about the relationship between having a high proportion of students with SEN in inclusive classrooms and the academic achievement of their peers. While Balestra, Eugster, and Liebert (2022) reported that when more than 15–20% of students in a classroom have SEN there was a negative effect on the academic outcome of their peers, Ruijs (2017) did not find an effect. The composition of the sample could provide an explanation. The Ruijs (2017) sample included the entire secondary school population of the Netherlands ($N = 524,457$), where about 1% had SEN and 99% did not. The Balestra, Eugster, and Liebert (2022) sample was made up of students from one Swiss canton ($N = 49,961$) where 25.5% of the students had SEN and 74.5% did not. It should be noted that the studies also had different definitions of SEN: Balestra, Eugster, and Liebert (2022) classified students as having SEN if they had a relationship with the school psychology service, not because of a diagnosis. This could explain the much higher proportion of students with SEN in the study.

According to Ruijs (2017) students with SEN are frequently placed in low-ability tracks. Often, there are few or no students with SEN in high-ability tracks. This means that there is a risk that the class composition in low-ability tracks might negatively affect the academic outcomes of students with and without SEN. Current policies on ability-based streaming in secondary schools therefore warrant critical examination (Balestra, Eugster, and Liebert 2022).

Limitations and future studies

This study has several limitations. We attempted to counteract language bias (Brunton et al. 2017) by searching for studies in English, French, and German. However, only one of the 21 studies was published in another language (German). The three studies from Germany were conducted by the same research group (Gebhardt, Heine, and Sälzer 2015, 2015; Jungjohann, Schurig, and Gebhardt 2023), potentially introducing a bias in the reported effects. Of the 21 studies, one each came from China and Singapore, eight from European countries, and eleven from English-speaking countries. Notably, positive effects were more often reported in US studies, while European studies more often reported neutral effects (Szumski, Smogorzewska, and Grygiel 2022). Contextual differences between the countries

(school system, definitions of inclusive and special education) and the sample size could also have affected the results (Szumski, Smogorzewska, and Grygiel 2022; Entrich 2021).

There is a great deal of heterogeneity in study methodology. Although all the studies had a quantitative design, their research strategies differed. In some studies, no information on effect sizes or error probability was available. Moreover, many of the studies were descriptive, relying on frequency comparisons and reporting correlational results. However, we decided to include studies of varying quality due to the rather small number of studies available.

Finally, this study had a narrow focus on academic achievement, excluding other important outcomes such as cross-curricular, adaptive, and social skills. Little is known about the influence of critical factors such as teacher-related variables, classroom processes, individual factors, and class composition (e.g. number of students with SEN per class). This review did not investigate the quality of the inclusive education or the extent of inclusive education implementation. Data on inclusive practice (e.g. teacher cooperation, differentiation) and its relationship to class composition were not available because the included studies provided little or no information about these factors. The absence of this information limits the interpretation of differences in academic outcomes. Recent research suggests that examining the effects of inclusive practices on student learning is complex and may yield mixed results (Schnepel et al. 2025). This highlights the need for further research on the quality and extent of inclusive education.

Conclusions

We conducted a systematic review of the literature examining the relationship between inclusive education and the achievement of students with and without SEN in secondary schools published between 2006 and 2025. Our findings highlight the importance of considering the type of SEN, the time students with SEN spend in mainstream classrooms, and the proportion of students with SEN in class. Additionally, more longitudinal data, which allows for better control of prior knowledge, would help mitigate placement effects.

The findings of this study provide evidence supporting the further promotion of inclusive education of students with SEN in secondary school. However, it is important to acknowledge that secondary education is shaped by various selection mechanisms (e.g. ability tracking), meaning that the advantage of inclusive education depends on the cognitive abilities of students. Therefore, further research is needed to better understand the conditions under which inclusive education is particularly effective within different school systems.

Note

1. The focus is on the inclusion of students with SEN. We do not consider the inclusion of other marginalised groups such as students with a migrant background or those who do not speak the language of instruction.

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